

FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH

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Abstract: *The focus of the article is human oral speech. Currently, the study of the influence of various factors on the speech signal is one of the main tasks of applied speech science. In the work, an attempt was made to identify the factors that affect the speech apparatus and speech of a person. To determine them, a review and analysis of the scientific literature of Russian and foreign authors was carried out. Given the complexity and complexity of the process of speech production, when analyzing the factors, the phenomenon of oral speech was considered from the point of view of different disciplines: narcology, psycholinguistics, anatomy, phonoscopy, psychiatry, otolaryngology, psychology. As a result of the study, a number of factors were identified that affect the speech apparatus and speech of a person as a whole. These include: defects in the structure of the articulatory organs, intoxication, age, disease, and emotional state. However, it should be noted that in some cases it is difficult to establish which of the factors caused certain speech changes. In addition, experiments in this area are difficult, given the difficulty of detecting a neutral emotional state, as well as the possibility of imitation of speech by the speaker.*

Keywords: *speech apparatus; speech; intoxication; age; emotional condition; diseases; articulatory defects.*

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is an important language skill to be learned by students at all levels of students. It is a verbal communication as it is produced by systematic verbal utterances to convey meanings, such as short conversation, dialogues and speech. It also can be used to express the student's ideas, opinions and feelings.

Brown states that speaking is the product of creative contraction of linguistics strings; the speaker makes choices of the lexicon, the structure, and discourse. In other words, speaking is the process of choosing and using the elements of language such as words, the structure of sentences, and discourse (Brown, 2004: 140).

In addition, there are several advantages when a student especially a senior high school student is good at speaking skill. The students can communicate effectively with

each other in daily conversation. They can speak well with their teachers, participate in the classroom activities, like in group discussion, present their task well in front of the class, participate in a local competition even international competition, and also able to participate in the broader world or international world .

Speaking has been taught in Indonesia for many years in many classes and levels of students. As Permendikbud No. 59 the year 2014 states that the purpose of learning speaking skill as a productive skill expects the students to be able to communicate effectively in verbal/oral, inside and outside of the school. The students are expected to be more communicative in using their verbal/oral in all situations.

The speech development of a child is a complex multidimensional process. It includes various aspects of a child's mastery of speech: psychological, neuropsychological, linguistic, pedagogical, and others. Each child normally goes through peculiar stages of mastering various aspects of speech development. Different authors distinguish a large number of classifications, stages, steps of each side of the speech development of a preschool child. These steps are conditional, since the development of each child proceeds individually and depends on various factors, but nevertheless, development is subject to general patterns that are characteristic of all children. The problem of speech development was studied by such scientists as L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev and others L.S. Vygotsky worked out the questions of the origin and development of speech. The authors point out that speech is one of the varieties of the sign. The appropriation of signs takes place in the process in substantive joint activity and through communication. The formation of oral speech occurs as the formation of activity. Consequently, as in any activity, the most important condition for the formation of oral speech is the development of the child's motivational side of speech activity. For the development of speech, it is necessary to form the need for communication through activities with objects of the surrounding world. Considering speech activity, it must be emphasized that the child's mental development occurs in the process of developing his activity, in the process of communication. Communication is a special kind of activity. The language process is the implementation of the activity approach to the process of speech formation. The activity approach presupposes speech activity itself.

The basis of the entire verbal development of the child is the communicative function of speech. The timely appearance of this function determines how soon the child masters the highest levels of consciousness and voluntariness of behavior.

I. Most researchers of speech focus on its actual side: pronunciation, lexical, grammatical and coherent speech. This is definitely important. But even more

interesting is the study of the factors in the development of speech, those driving forces that are not always noticeable, but play a leading role in it.

For the normal formation of speech activity, it is necessary to fully form its prerequisites. They can be divided into three main groups, namely, intact physiological and psychological bases, a favorable social environment.

METHODS

One of the most important factors of human speech development is a holistic physiological basis. It consists of a system for receiving information, central speech mechanisms, a sound-producing system, etc.

The information reception system provides primary reception and auditory perception of speech. In addition, it includes visual and tactile-kinesthetic channels. Hearing plays a leading role in the formation of speech. With his help, the child perceives the speech of others, imitates it and controls his pronunciation. The overall picture of the development of speech skills in a child can change significantly with a pronounced decrease in visual acuity, and certain articulation disorders can be associated even with minor defects in tactile sensitivity.

The central mechanisms of speech depend on the physiological integrity of the corresponding parts of the central nervous system and provide understanding, interpretation, formulation and programming of various linguistic aspects.

The sound-producing system consists of laryngeal, pharyngeal, nasal and oral structures, as well as neuromuscular mechanisms that provide changes in breathing for the purpose of pronouncing sounds, generation of laryngeal sound, formation of articulated sounds by changing the forms and parameters of the air flow in the pharynx, larynx and oral cavity. Any breathing disorders affect the sound-producing system. Anomalies of the larynx, pathology of resonant cavities lead to a change in the timbre of the voice. Changes in the posterior velum distort the structure of the nasal bands and lead to hypernasalization of sounds in children with soft and hard palate defects. Lips take an active part in the pronunciation of a number of consonant sounds. To pronounce many sounds, precise and fast movements of the tongue are necessary, so any restrictions on its mobility can significantly affect articulation.

An important condition for the timely and correct flow of speech development of children is a safe psychological base.

The human body is a complex interconnected system, therefore, mental processes have a huge impact on the formation of speech activity.

Undifferentiated, inactive perception, poor memory, unstable attention, low level of development of thinking - all this affects the quality of children's speech.

Another important factor in the full-fledged speech development of children is a favorable social environment. It provides interpersonal communication in all types of communication and is a language model for imitation.

RESULTS

Based on those theories above, it can be concluded that speaking is the active, productive skill that is used to express ideas in the form of speech sounds of the language. It can be said that speaking is a skill that commonly used in daily life between speaker and listener in performing the idea. Contributing factor is something partly responsible for development or phenomenon and something that influences the speaking area, there some factors that contribute to the development and improvement of speaking ability. These factors take a great position in influencing of students' speaking development and improvement. There are many arguments about the factors that contribute and influence students' speaking ability. First, Mahmoudi and Mahmoudi conclude the factors that contribute and influence students' speaking ability into two general groups. Those are internal and external factors. Internal factors are factors which come from inside the individual. Internal factors imply cognitive and affective factors such as motivation, intelligence, anxiety, risk-taking and ability (Mahmoudi & Mahmoudi , 2015). Many studies have confirmed that motivation correlates strongly with proficiency, indicating both that successful learners are motivated and that success improves motivation. Motivation has been recognized as an important variable determining students' achievement and attainment for a long time. Siegel in Mahmoudi and Mahmoudi state motivation is affected by learners' attitudes towards the second language, its speakers, and the speakers' culture (Mahmoudi & Mahmoudi , 2015). Alsayed in his research says that motivation seems to be the most significant predictor of overall performance in English as a foreign language. In the field of intelligence, Mirhadizadeh states that language may not be merely a vital link in the social side of intellectual development. Language may be the way foundation of intelligence itself. In relating intelligence to second language learning, it is concluded that intelligence is fixed at birth. Intelligence is the role of cognitive skills within specific strategies and appropriate context which frees us from the old fixed view about intelligence, thus, the learner can improve himself .

CONCLUSION

Taking into account the complexity and importance of speech in our life, in order to solve the problems of applied speech science , it is necessary to highlight its important aspects and features. Based on the analysis of scientific works of Russian

and foreign authors in a variety of disciplines, the following number of factors were identified that affect the speech apparatus and speech of a person as a whole, taking into account the interdisciplinarity of the “speech” phenomenon: - defects in the structure of articulatory organs; - intoxication; - age; – diseases; - emotional condition. However, we note that in some cases it is difficult to establish which of the factors caused certain changes in speech. In addition, experiments in this area are difficult, given the difficulty of detecting a neutral emotional state, as well as the possibility of imitation of speech by the speaker. It should also be noted that for fundamental studies of the speech signal, it is necessary to apply several different types of data analysis: acoustic, perceptual and linguistic.

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